

STUDENTS' CONCEPTUALIZATION ON CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS IN THEIR RESEARCH PROPOSAL AND FINAL PROJECT

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Abstract

The critical thinking skills of students are relatively low; this has implications for the low academic writing skills that are mastered by English foreign language (EFL) students. This study aims to describe in detail the ability to conceptualize critical thinking in relation to academic writing skills. The method used in this research is qualitative with a phenomenological approach. By employing qualitative research methods with the instruments of observation and interviews, this study scrutinized the existence of critical thinking skills performed by the students in their scientific writing, the conceptualization of critical thinking skills, and the difference between their conceptualization and practices. Through document observations and semi-structured interviews, this study found that the ability to prepare proposals and final projects for EFL students in Indonesia is still low, this is due to the low ability to think critically. The low critical skill is caused by the low literacy possessed by students both from reading books, the internet, triplets and their weakness in relating the aspects being discussed.

Keywords: critical thinking, academic writing, research proposal, final project

INTRODUCTION

The world-class forum reported that they were re-skilling by 2025 due to the technology increase in terms of digital dependencies and cyber vulnerabilities. There were four main skills of EFL learning that should be taken into account in developing the critical thinking skills of university students. One of them is accustoming the students to write scientifically so that they were able to go deep into various concepts beyond literal meanings (Itmeizeh & Hassan, 2020).

Without critical thinking skills, the students became narrow-minded and rigid in thinking. They could not adapt themselves successfully to unpredictable conditions or situations. They were unable to make the right decisions. Fortunately, EFL university students had many opportunities to develop their critical thinking skills through academic writing. Their research strengthened the statement of Hurley (2016) that critical thinking was the parent of good writing. He strongly believed that critical thinking skills supplied critical writing. Without having critical thinking skills, the writer could not proceed with information and ideas critically on papers (Safriyani et al, 2021).

Through the EFL teachers' voices found in their research, they found that writing facilitates students much on upgrading the students' critical thinking skills. In writing, there was a process of thinking or reasoning. Therefore, the quality of performing critical thinking skills affected the quality of composing writings. Tahira and Haider, (2019) proved that the academic writing process coached the EFL students to be accustomed to utilizing their

critical thinking skills. Having habits of performing critical thinking skills for university students was basically a collective work among lecturing courses. This means that improving students' critical thinking skills at universities required great cooperation between all lecturers of different subjects.

Pu (2021) stated that the process of composing academic writing set the EFL students in scientific experiences of observations, analysis, evaluation, reasoning, and other components of critical thinking skills. Academic writing was recognized as a valuable and efficient mode to boost EFL students' critical thinking skills. Unfortunately, the abilities of academic writing of Indonesian students were still low and unrecognized internationally. This was because the Indonesian students had been too long in speaking and listening activities so they were unable to write ideas in writing by using a good and systematic manner.

Academic writing became a scourge for university students since they were lack accustoming to upgrading their critical thinking skills through writing activities. They usually learned self-taught through papers, assignments, or scientific works of their seniors, which were also lacking accuracy. Therefore, their lecturers had the professional responsibility to improve their students' critical thinking skills, which was the most essential ingredient in producing qualified academic writing.

Whereas, many overseas universities specifically required higher writing scores than speaking. It was because the main challenge of attending world-class overseas universities was the ability to write academically. It was undeniable that the writing case was still the main handicapped Indonesian students when studying abroad. Most of them were stuck in terms of academic writing.

They were lacking in (1) presenting clear ideas on papers, (2) analyzing issues in detailed arguments, (3) evaluating supporting shreds of evidence, and (4) elaborating the discussion accurately. These main problems resulted from internal competencies, namely insufficiencies of (1) having awareness of the significant roles of critical thinking skills for their academic achievements, (2) comprehending the concept of critical thinking skills, and (3) understanding the differences between the academic requirements in British and in Indonesia.

Most Indonesian students deemed academic writing as a scary academic activity. This aggravated the situation that Indonesian students remained weak in academic writing. However, having research became an academic culture for international university students. They had to be able not only to produce academic writing periodically but also to publish them in reputable journals.

They were still incapable of utilizing critical thinking skills while composing their academic papers in terms of composing good arguments with excellent reasoning and accurate shreds of evidence (Reay, 2018). Without critical thinking skills, the students were unable not only to make premises effectively but also to do searching, analyze and evaluate ideas in their academic papers. Critical thinking skills enabled the students to select information and ideas,

choose the most appropriate, concise words and paragraphs, and deliver messages impressively in their academic writing.

Statements of the Problem

Due to the focus of this research on the effort of finding out the students' critical thinking performance in their academic writing, this research framed three research questions.

1. How did university students' self-reflection in writing competence?
2. How did university students conceptualize academic writing?
3. How is the competence of university students in applying academic writing in research proposals and final assignments?

Theory

Critical Thinking Skills

Steinberg, et. al., (2013) defines critical thinking as the specific thinking skills of identifying assumptions, clarifying, focusing, and being relevant to focused issues. Today, critical thinking skills are referred to the attitudes and habits of mind for reasoning with accurate evidence. Basically, critical thinking skills are considered as thinking activities with careful judgment or evaluation. For students, critical thinking skills become vital skills to develop to have good learning achievement since this skill encourages the students to do analysis to understand issues or information. This is why Putra, et. al., (2014) labels critical thinking skills as valuable tools for students to achieve successful study. Indeed, critical thinking skills are dealt with the intellectual development of conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and evaluating the collected information resulting from observations. The critical thinking approach is a method of analysis. It analyses all aspects of the practical research process. It does so by comparing with the literature and logical information. Furthermore, it provokes excellence in thoughts and puts them into paper. It also helps the scholar to identify the important aspects of research.

For EFL students, critical thinking skills force them to examine and consider every belief and information based on supporting shreds of evidence before making justifications. Therefore, the students are required to do interpretations, evaluation, observation, and argumentation to make qualified reasoning. Paul & Elder (2019:4) give several indicators of being critical thinkers. Critical thinkers are able to formulate problems clearly and precisely. They are capable to interpret issues, problems, or information correctly. They are effective and relevant in making the right conclusions. They are accurate in finding solutions based on the criteria and standards that she got from the evaluation. As critical thinkers, they are open-minded in recognizing and assessing assumptions, implications, and consequences to figure out effective and efficient solutions.

Critical Thinking and Reflective Thinking

Specifically, Iyer (2019) views critical thinking skills as the ability to transfer knowledge from one cognitive area to another cognitive area to get relevant information, solve problems effectively, and make decisions collaboratively based on appropriate information. Thus, critical thinking skills involve not only the processes of thinking but also the products of thinking. This is why critical thinking skills implicate a series of actions of questioning the credibility of information, making decisions to accept or reject the information, and recognizing significant occurrences based on the prior relevant knowledge (Yaiche,, 2021).

Critical thinking skills are characterized as the integration of skills and disposition. The skills relate to the abilities to analyze, evaluate, and make inferences, while the disposition deals with motivation and inclination. These natures of critical thinking skills are appeared in having meaningful critical thinking activities. The meaningful critical thinking skills activities involve the processes of thinking, making decisions, and solving problems (Facione, 2020).

Bennet (2018) establishes basic natures of critical thinking skills, namely dispositions, criterion, arguments, consideration or reasoning, point of view, and procedures for applying criteria. Dispositions as the natures of critical thinking skills belong to (1) having a skeptical attitude, (2) being open-minded, (3) appreciating honesty, (4) respecting various data and opposite arguments, (5) respecting clarity and thoroughness, (6) looking for other different views, and (7) moving to better logical opinions.

Research Proposal

Academic writing has many types and different names as writing assignments such as essays, assignment papers, research papers, work papers, research proposals, final project theses and dissertations, and others. However, academic writing has the same goals and principles (Yaiche, 2021).

One form of scientific writing prepared by students as a final project at the university is a research proposal. When the proposal is accepted by their supervisor, the students can continue the proposal to the final research projects such as thesis, thesis, and dissertation. The purpose of writing a proposal is to prepare a systematic, methodological, and logical research plan so that the students can conduct research correctly based on the schedule. Another goal is to train the students' abilities in expressing problems and main ideas used to conduct scientific research to solve the problems (Yuan, et.al,2020).

A research proposal is a scientific planning blueprint that contains the subject matter and methodology to prepare the final assignments as a contract agreement between the students as researchers and their supervisors (Tang, 2016). Other functions are (1) as a planning tool which shows that a person has a useful research project and that he has the competence and a good work plan to complete it, (2) to convince others such as other researchers, funding agencies, educational institutions, and supervisors that the proposed research is worthy of support, (3) to demonstrate the researcher's expertise and competence in a particular field of

study, and (4) as a contract between the various individuals and groups of people involved in it (Rohayati, 2021).

Research proposals have various types so each one has a relatively different format depending on its use. There are at least four kinds of research proposals related to the final project, namely quantitative research proposals, qualitative research proposals, classroom action research proposals, and research and development proposals. However, the four types of research proposals generally have a relatively similar systematic consisting of three parts, namely the initial part, core part, and final part (Sa'dijah, 2020).

Final Project

Academic writing that takes a relatively long time to write at the end of the study in order to complete the study at a university is known as the final project. There are various types of this final project according to the level of study taken by students, namely the theses for undergraduate students, theses for those at master programs, and dissertations for the students of doctoral programs. Most of colleges or universities require the students to make this final project according to the level of study they are taking. The final projects are written by the students based on the rules of writing style or techniques established by the universities which are different from one another. However, the basic structure remains the same (Samanhudi, 2019).

In addition, the final project is a research report as a form of independent course that discusses a topic in detail. The final project is written following predetermined academic writing rules. In its implementation, the students who are making the final project get guidance from the supervisor. With the guidance of the lecturer, it is hoped that the final project carried out by students will run smoothly so that it is completed correctly on time. The final project is declared complete when the student can account for their research in front of the examiner board (Sharadgah, 2014).

The final project has a different name depending on the level of education. For the undergraduate level (S1), the final project of academic writing in which the concepts, types, and writing steps are known as the thesis, for the postgraduate level (S2) it is called a thesis, and for the doctoral program (S3) it is known as a dissertation. A thesis is a scientific work written by undergraduate students as a form of a final project and as one of the graduation requirements. The output of the thesis is the students are able to develop their ideas, reasoning, experiences, and their scientific and practical knowledge based on the research that they have conducted (Shinta, 2020).

METHODS

RESEARCH DESIGN

The researcher used a descriptive qualitative method in this study. This method provided an explanation in the form of a description based on data and various scientific references (Wegerif, 2015). The data were collected, analyzed, and studied to produce a conclusion. In

another sense, a descriptive method was a method used to examine the status of a group of people, a condition, an object, or a condition of events that were occurred in a particular environment (Basrowi & Sudjarwo, 2006).

Research Setting

This research was conducted in the English Education Department of the Undergraduate Program at STKIP PGRI Sidoarjo. This private college gave a lot of opportunities for the researcher to do this study in order to give academic contributions to the institution, especially for the development of the lecturers and students. Having easier access to accomplishing this research became another factor for the researcher to choose this college as the setting of this study (Basrowi & Suwandi, 2008).

Research Subject

Therefore, this research involved 24 students from 2018 and 3 students from 2019 who submitted their final papers in Scientific Writing, gave self-reflection papers, and attended the students' interviews. The final papers of Scientific Writing for the students of 2018 were different from the final papers of Scientific Writing for the students of 2019.

Research Instruments

Therefore, there were three instruments used in this research. First, the instrument for answering the first research question was the document observation or analysis. It was for analyzing the existence of critical thinking skills in the students' scientific writing based on the indicators of critical thinking skills promoted by Facione (2020), Paul and Elder (2019), and Nuckles (2020). They were (1) analyzing arguments, claims or evidence made by the students in their final papers, (2) judging or evaluating based on evidence, (3) making inferences using inductive or deductive reasoning, (4) making decisions and/or solving problems through reasoning, (5) the focus where the clarity of the academic writing content is shown with clear subjects, issues, and themes, (6) clarity of argumentation, (7) reasoning where the explanations presented in the academic writing are supported by clear reasons and provide alternative arguments angle or point of view, (8) supporting reasons, where are the explanations and reasons that support ideas and sub-ideas that expressed in the academic writing, looks specific, accurate, and critical, (9) precision of the students' position as the writers, (10) relevance in providing data and evidence, (11) organization where the paragraphs are arranged together explicitly connected, and (12) accuracy in choosing the academic language.

Data and Source of Data

The researcher collected all of those data from three sources of data. They were the students' scientific writing, the students' self-reflection papers, and the students' interview. They were analyzed and observed to answer the three research questions of this study. The data collection technique was considered important for the success of this research. In order to get reliable data, the researcher organized certain techniques for collecting them (Sugiyono,

2006). She also observed the documents of students' self-reflection papers to find the conceptualization of critical thinking skills that they utilized in composing their scientific writing. She interviewed the students to gain information about why there was a difference between the practice and the conceptualization of critical thinking skills in producing scientific writing (Basrowi & Suwandi, 2008).

Data Collection Procedure

The researcher employed three data collection procedures. She took the textual analysis and interviewing. The process of collecting data for doing textual analysis consisted of two steps. First, the researcher took students' scientific writing randomly. She analyzed these randomly selected final papers for the existence of critical thinking skills performed by the students. Next, she did the document observation on the students' self-reflection papers. This was for having information about the conceptualization of critical thinking skills used by the students in their academic papers. The last procedure of collecting the research data in this research was interviewing the students directly one by one in the classroom documented by video recordings (Basrowi & Suwandi, 2009).

Every research required a standard to see the truth degree of truth in the research results. In qualitative research, this standard was often considered as data validity or trustworthiness. It was checking the validity of the data to eliminate the errors in the process of data acquisition which certainly had an effect on the validity of the final results of this study (Meleong, 2007).

The data validity or trustworthiness in this study was determined by using the criterion of the degree of confidence or credibility. This credibility was intended to prove that the research data collected by researchers was in accordance with the facts of the academic writing and the self-reflection papers written by the students of 2018 and 2019 in the English Education Department of the Undergraduate Program at STKIP PGRI Sidoarjo.

Data Analysis

The data analysis was done by the researcher by observing and analyzing the final papers, self-reflection papers made by the students, and interview results. The data analysis was crucial for having a very clear understanding of all of the collected data. This was a significant step toward the success of this research in answering the research questions and in achieving the research objectives. At this stage, the researcher did not reduce the collected data since the data was not numerous. The data were available in the students' final papers of Scientific Writing, the students' self-reflection saved in the Archives of the English Education Department, and the video recordings of direct interviews (Arikunto, 2002).

The basic principle of presenting data in this study was to share an understanding of the collected data with other people. This was why the data obtained in this qualitative research were displayed in the form of words or descriptions. Therefore, the researcher will make the presentation of data in the form of a narrative that could be easily understood by the reader (Sutopo, 2002).

Drawing conclusions was the final part of the data analysis in this study. It was the activity of interpreting the data. This data interpretation aimed at finding the meaning of the data that were presented. The interpretation was done by the researcher by finding patterns and themes (Miles & Huberman, 1992).

RESEARCH FINDING

Student self-reflection in writing competence

The student of 1888203027 was not clear enough to understand that in qualitative research the process of data analysis and interpretation required creative, critical, and very careful thinking. The two processes were interrelated and very closely related. Data analysis was a process for organizing data in order to obtain patterns or forms of regularity. Meanwhile, data interpretation was the process of giving meaning to the patterns or regularities found in her study. Therefore, the data collected was expected to be the answer to the research questions that she had formulated. The process of compiling data could vary between the researchers depending on taste, experience, and creative thinking so that the collected data could influence the selection of data analysis tools. In qualitative research, there was no definite formula for analyzing data such as the formula used in quantitative research. She forgot that inferencing like another component of critical thinking skills was the autonomous action of a researcher or writer when he needed to do inference based on the collected qualitative data and when he analyzed the data qualitatively. Indeed, data analysis in qualitative research was a continuous process. Data collection and data analysis run simultaneously (Bogdan & Biklen in Zamakhasari et al, 2020).

Uniquely another student that was quite well at understanding the concept of critical thinking skills in the previous elaboration of his self-reflection papers also was not clear enough about the inference and how to do inferencing in his writing. He, the student of 1988203024, believed that inferencing in his writing related to the writing activity under the guidance of his supervisor or lecturer. He did not understand that inference was basically the ability to judge the quality of conclusions based on the assumption of reasons to be accepted. Therefore, he could make appropriate conclusions based on his accuracy in choosing reasons to support the conclusions that he had made. He misconceptualized about the inference that was seen in this part of his self-regulation papers captured in this study below.

Similar to the previous student, the student of 1988203032 showed contradictive explanations in her self-reflection papers. When she explained the critical thinking components that she already applied in her scientific writing, she was good at doing the explanation by providing appropriate evidence to support her explanation. Contradictively, she was failed in explaining the essence of critical thinking skills that she already performed in her scientific writing. These two screenshots showed a contrary understanding of critical thinking skills.

She missed in explaining that critical thinking skills were not only activities about the opinion that she was researching. Writing scientific papers was also not only about writing a research paper. Basically, writing was a critical process wherein writing the writer also involved

higher-order thinking processes, namely analysis, synthesis, and evaluation called critical thinking skills (Facione, 2020).

The student of 1988203032 disregarded that the interpretation that she already mentioned in her self-reflection paper was not the opinion that was being researched. In writing scientific papers, the interpretation occurred when she understood from various experiences including the activities of categorizing, decoding, explaining, recognizing problems without prejudice, and distinguishing main ideas from additional ideas from the information sources. The analysis that she already performed in her scientific writing was when she identified the intended and inferential relationship between the statements of reading resources, and the examination of ideas, analysis of arguments, and identified invalid assumptions. written. The evaluation that she also already conducted was her ability to consider the credibility of assumptions and compare the strengths and weaknesses of alternative views based on her beliefs. The inference that she already made referred to the ability to construct meaning and to identify the implications of a particular position.

The interesting finding when analyzing the conceptualization of critical thinking skills of the students in their scientific writing was the statement expressed by the student of 1888203028 in his self-reflection paper. He misunderstood the questions of self-reflection stated on the first page. He answered “Big No” to the question “Did you do interpretation when writing your final papers?”. He gave the reason for the Big No answer by stating “This paper should be originally English so I could register it on an international journal platform”. This reflected that he totally believed that interpretation in critical thinking skills is the same as language interpretation or language translation. However, he claimed that he did the analysis by giving the proper reason and appropriate example of analysis that he already performed in his scientific writing. All of these could be seen in this screenshot of the first page of his self-reflection paper.

Conceptualization of student competence in writing

A similar case also happened to the student as seen on the YouTube at <https://youtu.be/vCqlpf0kuDA>. He did not do totally in accomplishing his scientific writing because he had spent all of his time, energy, and concentration on finishing the project of drama as the final product of the literature subject. His roles were as the drama scriptwriter and the play director for this literature project. He admitted that he did not prepare well in composing his scientific writing. He realized that there were several elements of critical thinking skills that he did not explore well in his scientific writing. He paid for the mistakes by producing a scientific article after doing the reflection through his self-reflection paper. Now he is in the process of finishing his scientific article for his undergraduate graduation.

A different case showed in the interview of the students at <https://youtu.be/vCqlpf0kuDA>. She did not have enough prior knowledge about critical thinking skills in writing. After having a self-reflection paper, she was triggered to literate herself in-depth in order to enrich her knowledge about critical thinking skills in composing a scientific paper. She improved herself in exploring her critical thinking skills by writing a scientific article that was

published in one of the Sinta 4's journals after that. This interview showed that the student had an internal factor, namely a lack of knowledge about critical thinking skills that made her could not explore them much in her scientific writing.

Another internal factor that caused the difference between the conceptualization and writing practice was owned by the student. This was seen at https://youtu.be/8PzUnt_EtPo. She admitted that she was lacking practice in using critical thinking skills on scientific papers. After writing her self-reflection, she was directed to practice more performing critical thinking skills on scientific papers. She took the self-reflection papers as guidance in practicing critical thinking skills on papers.

In order to produce scientific papers precisely with high quality, the students must pay attention to every detail attached to the writing. One thing that was important and also very basic for the students to understand well was exploring their critical thinking skills in writing their scientific papers. In addition, they must also understand the meaning of the concept of critical thinking skills as well as the conceptualization and operationalization of critical thinking skills which was closely related to having a critical discussion in their scientific papers.

Understanding the basic meaning and components of critical thinking skills played major implications for the success of writing scientific papers. This helped the students easier to convey the intent or results of their thoughts and arguments. Unfortunately, some of the students in this research did not pay attention to this matter. Other students still did not understand the process of conceptualization and operationalization so there was a blurring between the two decreasing the quality of their scientific papers.

To facilitate the researcher of this study in understanding the concept of critical thinking skills owned by the students, the researcher analyzed the student's written expressions in their self-reflection papers. When the students started their writing with abstract statements, this referred to the birth of an abstract concept. The students might also start their writing by building assumptions of critical thinking skills in which there was a prediction of the relationship between elements referring to the concept. The emerging concept was then further elaborated so that the abstract status could be changed to a concrete concept (Manheim and Rich in Lukin, 2017). The action of constructing the concept of critical thinking skills was referred to as conceptualization.

Basically, conceptualization was the process of introducing and explaining concepts. This was why conceptualization could be interpreted as a process of building a higher or more general concept from several existing concepts. Some of the students in this research were able in conceptualizing critical thinking skills correctly since they already had a defined concept of critical thinking skills. They could show their correct conceptualization through detailed explanations in their self-reflection papers. They were also able to support their correct explanations with relevant evidence. It could be said that the conceptualization of critical thinking skills that the students already put forward in their self-reflection papers was

a process of identifying and explaining concepts where the students determine what they meant by critical thinking skills.

The conceptualization of critical thinking skills by students in this study contained a combination of processes in (1) knowing the meaning of critical thinking skills that have been understood which is indicated by explaining critical thinking appropriately without ambiguity, ambivalence, ambiguity, and inaccuracy, (2) having a critical picture thinking skills that have been understood, and (3) expressing the main characteristics of critical thinking skills correctly. The conceptualization was the intellectual process of the students in forming their concepts about critical thinking skills. Thus, conceptualization was the students' understanding of critical thinking skills including the definition, components, function, and implementation.

The conceptualization was different from operationalization. In contrast to conceptualization, operationalization could be defined as the process of breaking down general concepts into more specific concepts. Operationalization was an important part of research writing activities. This was because the operationalization process made the students focus on explaining the phenomenon being discussed. Operationalization was closely related to the observation process. In carrying out the operationalization, the students must be able to connect the concept with the observation itself. The observation was done to obtain information, data, values, or characteristics inherent in the phenomenon being discussed. Operationalization was also related to variables because the measurement in observation is intended to measure the value of a variable.

Thus, the concept of critical thinking skills could be understood as a form of abstraction from critical thinking skills so that it can be more easily understood and generally agreed. The students might build the higher concept from several existing concepts of critical thinking skills to describe the more general abstraction of critical thinking skills. This process was known as conceptualization. While the process that was opposite to conceptualization was popular as operationalization. This was the process of translating general concepts into more detailed or specific concepts. The operationalization process itself could be carried out after the students made observations to obtain data that could help the students to break down the general concepts into specific ones.

Through analyzing the students' self-reflection papers, this research found that the conceptualization of critical thinking skills in producing scientific writing was explained and elaborated well by most of the students in several indicators of critical thinking skills. All of the students described well about choosing their topics of scientific papers. They made decisions of selecting the topics based on the literature reviews that they had discussed with their lecturers. They supported their explanation with a good reasoning of why they chose the topics. All of them also told well about their experiences in deciding the topics of their scientific writing. Unfortunately, not all of the students had a correct understanding about doing interpretation in composing scientific writing. Most of the students failed in explaining what the interpretation was. They did not know the meaning and the roles or advantages of interpretation in writing their scientific papers. Most of them admitted that they did not do

interpretation in composing their scientific writing. However, a few of them could explain the interpretation in writing although they failed in providing the interpretation that they had performed in their scientific papers.

Additionally, some students in this study were able to do analysis scientifically. They were also good at giving correct proof from their scientific writing about the analysis that they had already performed. The inability of doing analysis resulted from the inability of doing the interpretation. The students could not analyze logically since they were not engaged in the process of the interpretation. As a result, they failed not only in doing inferences but also in constructing objective conclusions. They tended over-generalization. Most of the students also could not do evaluation correctly.

Competence in writing research proposals and final Assignments

Each student is required to make a research proposal before conducting research. After the research proposal is approved by the advisor, the students must carry out the research activities in which the research results are compiled into a thesis. Thesis writing is one of the mechanisms for disseminating the research results to the public (UGM Thesis Guide, 2015). In addition, the task of writing a thesis is to train students to put the results of their research activities methodologically, logically, and systematically into a written scientific work. A thesis is a research paper that is prepared as a final project for master's program students (S2). The term thesis is also a statement or a theory that is supported by arguments and put forward in an academic paper in order to get a master's degree. Meanwhile, a dissertation is a research paper prepared as a final project for a doctoral student. The dissertation tries to create a new theory and also tests the hypotheses based on pre-existing theories. The difference between a thesis and a dissertation lies in the depth of discussion of the research results (UNJ, 2018).

Writing the final project, namely theses, and dissertations, can be carried out in three forms. They are (1) field research on empirical research or laboratory, (2) research-based on case studies, and (3) literature review research. The final project with the research activities is a written work based on the empirical or original study. This research type can be in the forms of experimental research, theory development, copyright research, and survey research. This type of research may include a secondary analysis that tests hypotheses by presenting an analysis of data that has not been previously reported. This form of thesis is generally preferred by most university students.

The final project in the form of a case study is a written work of case material obtained when working with others. A case study describes a problem, indicates a way to solve the problem, and/or provides suggestions for further research, clinical application, or theory. Case studies must be prepared by maintaining a balance between presenting the illustrative material and using the case material that is confidential and responsible. The final project is in the form of a literature review which includes research synthesis and meta-analyses a critical evaluation of published literature. In a meta-analysis, the researchers use quantitative procedures to statistically combine the results of their studies. By organizing, integrating, and evaluating

the published literature, the researcher explains the progress of the research towards the clarification of a problem. In other words, the researcher (1) defines and clarifies the problem, (2) summarizes the previous research, (3) identifies the relationships, contradictions, gaps, and inconsistencies in the literature, and (4) suggests further activities to address the problem.

EFL students are infused to do the detailed analysis so that they can understand the concepts or new information. This leads the students to have efforts of separating significant facts from opinions correctly. Consequently, they are prompted to recognize unclear facts. This avoids the EFL students to make incorrect conclusions based on objective reasoning. The critical thinking activities in composing academic texts boost significantly the development of critical thinking skills (MOE, 2013; Madhvan et al, 2017).

Another nature of critical thinking skills is having a proper point of view. Basically, this is the way of looking at or interpreting information, problems, or issues for having the construction of meaning. Therefore, critical thinkers are willing to look at a phenomenon from different perspectives. Having procedures for implementing criteria or standards is another characteristic of critical thinking skills. This nature is actually very complex actions. This involves the critical thinkers to formulate definite problems, determine the right decisions, and identify approximations.

Academic writing, according to Elbow in Shinta & Filia (2020), is about expressing arguments with accurate reasons and valid evidence. Therefore, academic writing requires performing critical thinking skills toward the discussed topic. Indeed, academic writing reflects critical thinking skills (Ennis, 1993 in Laabidi, 2021). This indicates that academic writing requires academic competencies to achieve good academic texts. The competencies relate to significant attitudes of both critical thinkers and critical writers to organize and to perform excellently adjusted with various linguistic features required to create reputable writing.

Additionally, academic writing has a number of purposes for students, including (1) disseminating some thoughts and findings and justifying the answers with logic and some evidence; (2) developing skills of conducting research, evaluating information, organizing ideas, stating strong arguments, responding to other people's arguments, analyzing, and expressing thoughts clearly in written form; and (3) presenting information in order to display a clear understanding of a particular subject persuasively, and the like.

DISCUSSIONS

Students' Conceptualization of Critical Thinking Skills in Writing

The students' self-reflection papers showed that most of the students did explanations properly. Some of the students admitted that they were unable to do explanations. This made the students could not present information systematically. They failed in showing the relationship between information, facts, or data. They also were not able to see the cause and effect among the evidence. Uniquely, their self-reflection papers also showed that they could

do reasoning correctly. Some of the students could do argumentation logically after being able to do literature reviews appropriately. This following graphic described in details the students' conceptualization of critical thinking skills in their self-reflection papers.

The interesting finding of this study was about the conceptualization of critical thinking skills by the students was different from their practices of using critical thinking skills in writing their scientific papers. There were two factors underlying the difference. They were internal and external factors. The internal factors were dealt with the students' conceptual understanding of critical thinking skills completed with definition, components, functions, characteristics, and how to implement them in writing, the students' incapacibilities of using critical thinking skills in writing, and the students' lacking practices of using critical thinking skills in scientific writing.

The internal factors related to the students' understanding of critical thinking skills, the students' in capabilities of using critical thinking skills in writing, the students' misconception about critical thinking skills, and less practice of using critical thinking skills in scientific writing. While the external factors were dealt with the due time of submission, workload as employees which was not balanced with their study, and lack of guidance in performing critical thinking skills on scientific papers.

There were two types of understanding that were popular in the educational context. They were the conceptual understanding and the concept mastery (Dahar in Putra et al, 2014). The conceptual understanding could be interpreted as a process, action, and way for the students to truly understand or to exactly know about critical thinking skills. The students could be considered to have well understanding when they extremely understood critical thinking skills. While the mastery of concepts was the ability of the students to understand the meaning scientifically both in theory and its application in everyday life. Meanwhile, according to Bloom's definition of mastery of concepts, it was the ability to capture meanings of (1) being able to express a material presented in a more understandable form, (2) being able to provide interpretation, and (3) being able to apply it.

Based on what Facione (2020) believed that critical thinking skills were basically a descriptive description detail of several characteristics which included the process of interpretation, analysis, evaluation, inference, explanation, and self-regulation, this research found several things that were common characteristics of the student's critical thinking skills must be used in producing their scientific writing.

Basically, analytical thinking required practice. Analyzing is the skill of breaking down material into its parts and determining how the parts are connected between parts to create a concept (Bairagya & Joy, 2021). Indeed, by having analytical skills, the students could think wisely and smartly in solving problems by analyzing, remembering, and using information (Belecina & Ocampo, 2018; Ricco et al., 2020).

According to Ulger (2018), they are (1) giving reasons why the argumentation against a problem is reasonable, (2) analyzing statements and providing examples that can support or contradict, (3) using the supporting data to explain, (4) making and evaluating the general

conclusions based on the results of investigations and research, (5) making the definite conclusions or decisions from appropriate information, and (6) considering the validity of arguments using the inductive and deductive thinking. These relate to the indicators of analytical skills suggested by Permana et.al (2019) that the students must have. They are (1) analyzing problems by recognizing problems and exploring problems, (2) collecting information through knowing sources of information and distinguishing relevant and irrelevant information, (3) identifying risks and consequences by analyzing information and the consequences of what happened, (4) determining alternative problem-solving options through identifying options and identifying results, and (5) re-examining by concluding the answers that have been obtained correctly.

Conceptualize Academic Writing Of University Students

In this study, it was clear that the students who performed differently between their conceptualization and their practices of critical thinking skills in writing were assumed as understanding the concept of critical thinking skills, not as mastering the concept of critical thinking skills. There were four indicators shown by the students who understood the concept of critical thinking skills. They were (1) the students restated the definition of critical thinking skills, (2) the students were able to give correct examples of critical thinking components, (3) the students were confident in expressing their opinions about critical thinking skills correctly, and (4) the students were able to explain the functions of using critical thinking skills in their scientific writing.

In Bloom's cognitive domain taxonomy, the understanding was divided into three aspects, namely translation, interpretation, and extrapolation. The translation was the ability to change certain symbols into other symbols without changing the meaning. In this case, the symbols in the form of words were converted into pictures or charts, or graphs. When the symbol was in the form of certain words or sentences, it could be changed into other words or sentences. The transfer of concepts formulated from words into graphics could be included in the category of translating. While the interpretation was the ability to explain the meaning contained in symbols. This was also the ability to explain certain concepts, principles, or theories. The students could interpret a concept or principle when they could explain in detail the meaning of a concept or principle, or they could compare, distinguish, or contrast it with others. Whereas extrapolation was the ability to see the trend or direction or continuation of a finding. This type of understanding demanded the students' higher intellectual abilities such as making predictions about what might happen.

Mastering concepts was the ability of the students to understand the meaning scientifically both in theory and its application. In this case, the students were able to not only understand the meaning of critical thinking skills perfectly but also implement the concepts into real practice. Therefore, the difference between understanding the concept and mastering the concept was in the application of the concept. When the students understood the concept of critical thinking skills, they were able to understand the concept only without being able to implement the critical thinking skills in their writing practices. Meanwhile, when the

students mastered the concepts of critical thinking skills, they were able to apply the concepts to their writing activities.

The external factor of lack of practice in using critical thinking skills in scientific papers caused the difference in students' conceptualization and writing practices of critical thinking skills. The lack of practice in using critical thinking skills in writing resulted in some negative impacts on their writing products. They became less able to analyze problems which were from identifying and distinguishing components and assumptions to seeing something behind the existing ideas in order to reach the truth and coherence in the essay. The students also became less able to reconstruct and develop ideas that were clear and easy to understand. They were also unable to see and decide on information based on clear and reasonable criteria which are relevant to the content of their writing. Without having sufficient practice in using critical thinking skills of scientific papers, the students were not able to analyze problems logically. They could not relate problems to one another and see weak points that others might overlook.

Scientific reasoning was the ability to think systematically and logically to solve problems using the scientific method, including the process of evaluating facts, making predictions and hypotheses, determining and controlling variables, designing and conducting experiments, collecting data, analyzing data, and drawing conclusions so that it was needed to be trained (Saad et al., 2017).

In writing academic papers, scientific reasoning was the ability to conclude based on existing evidence. The reasoning was the process of describing conclusions from evidence (Stainberg and Cormier, 2013). Wegerif et al (2015) added that the reasoning ability is a provision for students to give reasons for opinions, actions to draw conclusions, make decisions, and use appropriate language in explaining their thoughts based on facts.

The thinking process in scientific reasoning was related to understanding concepts, argumentation, and problem-solving skills that could help students face the challenges of globalization and technological developments (Fischer et al in Berndt, Markus et al, 2021). According to Lawson in Tereza (2021), there were six aspects of scientific reasoning, namely (1) conservation reasoning; (2) proportional reasoning; (3) control of variables; (4) probability reasoning; (5) correlation reasoning; and (6) hypothetical-deductive reasoning. The characteristics of intellectual maturity according to Drost (2003:37) were being able to reason and speak maturely referred to as master orthography, grammar, and syntax of the language.

Competence in writing research proposals and final Assignments

Synthesis was another important action that the students must take in composing their final papers. Synthesis was one of the critical thinking skills to put parts together for creating something new. Synthesis indicators were the ability to use old knowledge or ideas into new things, combine ideas into new things, and use knowledge in new or different contexts.

In the synthesis section for writing scientific papers, the students could come up with new ideas to solve the problems that they found. In this case, they could broadly comment, discuss, or otherwise take the form of an argumentative. Speculation might be allowed within certain limits in composing scientific writing. The results of this synthesis were basically in the form of data, facts or information, or new ideas, which have never been written by other writers. This was basically the essence of their scientific papers. If the students only collected information, then this was not scientific work. This meant that the students did not generate new ideas in their academic writing products.

In composing academic writing, the students also needed to evaluate information from reading sources to collect relevant evidence or data. They had to do a series of evaluations and verification for meaningful information or data. In the digital era, everyone could publish or share information at will on the internet without requiring any qualifications. True information was mixed with personal opinion, fictitious stories, or disinformation. It was conveying false information on purpose to confuse others. Therefore, as internet users and novice writers who need a lot of information to support the writing being made, the students must be good at sorting out information. In this case, critical thinking skills are very important when the students were looking for online information online, especially the ability to evaluate information.

The students needed to compare its findings to other related sources. This meant that the students must not rely on one source of information only. The last was evaluating the date of sources. The students should consider the date of publication, updating, and revision. The students should also evaluate the date of the reference list provided in the source.

Thus, the students had to evaluate the information sources that they wanted to use in their academic writing for having relevant and reputable information. They need to identify (1) the authority of the sites, (2) the currency of the information, (3) the objectivity of the information, (4) accuracy, and (5) relevancy. These five indicators must be evaluated or identified deeply to get valid information from credible sources.

In identifying the authority, the students needed to recognize the parties behind the articles that they were reading. This helped the students to find who was behind the sites and who wrote the article. There were several ways to evaluate the sites. First, the students could check the address (URL) of the sites and see the domain ending such as .id, .com, etc. which could sometimes help the students to identify the type of organization behind the website. Second, the students could also check the pages of 'About Us' or 'About' to see the organization, company, or individual that had run and sponsored the site so that the students could have clear information about the identity of the sites such as addresses, phone numbers, or contact email. Next, the students could check whether the party running the site had a good reputation. This could be done by cross-checking via Google to see other sources that explained the reputation of the sites.

The students must also identify the author of the article because the author of the article was often not the same person as the administrator who run the site. The author's name usually

appeared at the beginning or end of the article. The article was sometimes accompanied by a brief biography of the author. To evaluate the writer or author of the article, the students had to identify (1) whether the author uses his real name or not, (2) what are the author's qualifications, (3) whether he is an expert in his field or not, (4) whether the author belongs to a particular institution, organization, or company or not, and (5) whether the students could find the article in another different site or not.

Evaluating the accuracy of the information was a must for the students in composing their final papers. This was because the accuracy of an article reflected whether the information submitted was true, accurate, and trustworthy. Accuracy could be seen from two aspects, namely the writing technique and the content. The students could pay attention to two things, namely whether there were spelling errors and whether the text was written well with correct grammar. In terms of content, accuracy could be recognized from (1) whether the content got the editing or review process, (2) whether the author included references to the information he wrote, (3) whether the reference source was accessible and reliable, and (4) if the author included data and facts from the research or investigation itself, then whether the method was clearly explained or not.

Another component of critical thinking skills that must be mastered well by the students in producing their academic writing was self-regulation. This referred to how to control and direct the actions (Taylor, 2009: 133). As novice writers, the students should be able to control themselves to remain objective in their writing presentations. They should also be able to direct their presentation to achieve their writing goals. In line with that, Zimmerman and Schunk (in Schunk, 2012:35) viewed self-regulation referred to the process by which individuals systematically direct thoughts, feelings, and actions to achieve goals. Then Schunk (2012:35) also added that researchers from different theoretical traditions assumed that self-regulation meant having goals and objectives, taking goal-directed actions, monitoring strategies, and goal-directed actions, and ensuring their success.

In addition, Alwisol (2009:285) stated that self-regulation was an ability possessed by humans in the form of the ability to think in order to manipulate the environment to reach a goal. According to Bandura (in Alwisol, 2009:285), there would be reactive and proactive strategies in self-regulation. Another obvious indicator of having analytical skills was that the students as critical thinkers were capable of analyzing their arguments, identifying their assumptions, and assessing the validity of results (Dafrita, 2017).

Conclusion

Based on the result and discussion can be concluded: First, University student used critical thinking skills to make the right decisions and to give the right reasons. Through implementing critical thinking skills, the students were engaged in the cognitive processes of making reasonable or logical decisions and the right decisions. They resulted from interpretation, analysis, evaluation, and inference to solve problems, formulate conclusions, make possible desired outcomes, and make decisions.

Second, academic writing skills were greatly influenced by critical thinking skills. The ability to think critically could be trained with the high practice of writing academically and scientifically. In preparation, the academic papers were indispensable for finding and concluding a problem objectively and scientifically. The higher the critical thinking skills, it could be even better in writing academic writing. The habit of using critical thinking skills was very necessary during the process of composing academic papers.

Third, by implementing the proposal research design and final paper. This implementation analyzed the existence of students' critical thinking skills in scientific writing. The data for this research were the students' scientific writing and self-reflection that they collect in the Scientific Writing course. This research analyzed their self-reflection documents to find out their understanding of the use of critical thinking skills in their scientific writing. Then they were interviewed about the differences between the practices of implementing critical thinking skills in scientific writing and their understanding of performing critical thinking skills in final papers. The researcher used semi-structured interviews to find the differences between the conceptualization and practices of utilizing critical thinking skills in final writing.

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